

New insights into the biogeography and taxonomy of ants in the *Tetramorium solidum*-group (Hymenoptera: Formicidae)

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BACKGROUND

Ants emerged during the Cretaceous period ca. 100 million years ago¹. This diverse group, currently comprising 12649 species², represent one of the most ecologically successful groups globally.

Ants within *Tetramorium solidum*-group are mainly restricted to the dry regions of southern Africa³. Despite the *T. solidum*-group's apparent ecological importance as seed predators, nothing is known about their biogeography and ecology.

AIMS

- * Revise *Tetramorium solidum*-group taxonomy.
- * Model predicted distribution of the group in southern Africa and identify climatic factors limiting their current distribution.
- * Use phylogeny to infer historical processes that shaped the group's diversity and endemism in southern Africa.

METHODS

- Morphology and development of identification key.
- Mitochondrial gene phylogeny (Bayesian).
- Divergence times estimated using fossil-calibrated phylogeny.
- SDMs using correlative approaches.

RESULTS

Fig. 1 mtDNA phylogeny indicating at least four new species to science. The fossil calibrated phylogeny suggest the *Tetramorium solidum* group is around 30 MY old.

Fig. 2 (a) The Namakaroo ecoregion is the center of species richness and endemism. (b,c) distribution of *T. solidum*-group is mainly influenced by rainfall and aridity except for one species, *T. setuliferum* (d).

CONCLUSIONS

Higher species diversity than previously thought: four new species described from our data. The group originated in the eastern parts of southern Africa but diversified in western southern Africa. Diversification of grasslands and the onset of aridification during the Oligocene-Miocene likely drove diversification within the *Tetramorium solidum*-group.